

Developing a CNN-Based Model for Automated Detection of Anthracnose Disease in Spinach Leaves

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PAPER KEYWORDS

Anthracnose disease,
Spinach, Machine
Learning, Artificial
Intelligence, Deep
learning

ABSTRACT

*Spinach (*Spinacia oleracea* L.) is a kind of vegetable that is widely cultivated for its economic purposes. However, the production of this vegetable is being threatened by a plant disease called the anthracnose disease, causing significant yield loss and reducing its market quality. The traditional methods used to detect anthracnose disease in spinach plants rely on manual inspection by experts, which is time-consuming and prone to human error. Different researchers have also applied more sophisticated methods like advanced machine learning and deep learning methods but mostly focused on general plant disease and multi-disease detection and failed to consider architectures tailored to specific diseases like anthracnose, which requires finer discrimination of lesion features. To address this gap from previous studies, this study developed a model that can detect anthracnose disease early in spinach plants for effective management and sustainable production. This study utilised the CNN algorithm on an image dataset collected from different spinach leaves. The dataset used contained 1,200 spinach leaf images categorised into five classes, including Bacterial Spot, Downy Mildew, Healthy, Pest Damage, and Anthracnose, which were preprocessed and used to train the CNN algorithm. During the data preprocessing, a data augmentation method was used to address data imbalance and improve model robustness. Google Colab was used to implement the proposed model in this study, and the development was done using the Python programming language. The model was further optimised with the use of parameters such as batch size, learning rate, and number of epochs. The performance of the proposed model was evaluated with the use of standard evaluation metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and f1-score, while visualisation of the result was done with the use of a confusion matrix and training-validation plots. The experimental result shows that the proposed model was able to achieve an accuracy of 95.00%, a precision of 96.00%, a recall of 95.00%, and an F1-score of 95.00%, showing the model's strong ability to detect anthracnose disease in spinach leaves under diverse conditions. This study's findings show that the adoption of a CNN-based model for spinach disease detection is highly effective, contributing to precision agriculture and supporting the goals of Agriculture 4.0 through intelligent, automated, and sustainable crop health monitoring systems.*

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19855367>

1.1. Introduction

Spinach (*Spinacia oleracea* L.), known for its nutrient-rich nature, is a kind of vegetable that is mostly produced for its dietary and economical purpose (Balasubramaniam et

al., 2025). The production of Spinach always faces a challenge of different leaf diseases, particularly Anthracnose. Anthracnose disease always causes severe yield loss in Spinach and reduces its market quality (Liu et al. 2021). To ensure effective management of Spinach and prevent its damage on a large scale, early and accurate detection of Anthracnose disease in this crop is essential (Nasarullah et al 2022). Researchers have applied different traditional methods to detect anthracnose disease in spinach, but these traditional methods rely heavily on visual inspection by experts, and are therefore time-consuming and prone to human error (Khakimov et al., 2022).

The recent advancement in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Computer Vision continues to gain popularity in agriculture and has revolutionised agricultural practices, as they have the ability to automatically detect disease in plants through deep learning techniques (Ghazal et al., 2024). Deep learning algorithms like the Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have been utilised by different researchers to recognise complex visual patterns in plant leaves, and have proven effective and accurate, producing results that outperform the traditional machine learning algorithms like Support Vector Machines (SVM), Decision Trees (DT) and Random Forests (RF) (Vakalopoulou et al., 2023). Over the years, the CNN model has significantly evolved, laying the foundation for modern computer vision systems through convolutional pooling hierarchies (Albawi et al., 2017). The continuous advancement in CNN architectures has led to the development of more sophisticated models like VGG, ResNet, and DenseNet to enhance feature representation and scalability (Khan et al., 2020). Transfer learning techniques continue to improve CNN adaptability across diverse agricultural and environmental datasets (Zhuang et al., 2021). Different researchers have conducted different studies (eg, Sennan et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2024; Bhavsingh et al., 2024) that applied CNNs and hybrid models for spinach and other crop disease detection, with high accuracies. However, most of these studies mainly focused on general leaf classification or multi-disease detection, which are not always feasible for specific diseases like Anthracnose.

To address these limitations from the existing studies, this study develops a detection model that can detect anthracnose disease in spinach leaves, using a CNN algorithm. The study enhances the performance of the proposed model by integrating data augmentation techniques to address data imbalance. This approach aims to improve model generalisation and robustness in identifying anthracnose under diverse image conditions. This study outcome is expected to contribute to precision agriculture by supporting the development of intelligent, automated systems for crop health monitoring, aligning with the goals of Agriculture 4.0 and sustainable food production. The rest of this research includes the related work section, which shows the review of previous studies related to this study, the methodology section, which shows the adopted method in this study, the experimental result section, which shows the results from the experiment performed in this study, the discussion section, which discusses the results, and the conclusion section, where the study is concluded.

Literature Review

Sennan et al. (2022) conducted research that focused on the development of a CNN-based model for spinach leaf classification. The study trained the model with the use of

a dataset that contains 400 images of four different categories of spinach leaves, which are Amaranth, Black nightshade, Curry leaves, and Drumstick leaves. The result from the experiment shows that the proposed CNN model was able to achieve 97.5% accuracy rate, outperforming the compared machine learning-based models.

Meena et al. (2022) utilised the CNN algorithm for the development of an early disease detection in 5 different plants, which are tomato, hibiscus, spinach, mango tree, and bitter melon. The dataset was subject to stages like image preprocessing, segmentation, and feature extraction, before the model training. The result of the experiment shows that the CNN-based model was able to achieve an accuracy of over 90%

Xu et al. (2024) utilised a method that combines CNNs with a spatial attention mechanism to enhance feature representation for spinach leaf disease detection. The experiment classification was achieved with the use of a SoftMax layer. The result from the experiment shows that the proposed CNN-based model was able to achieve 95.12% accuracy for the spinach disease detection. Recent studies focused on enhancing the discrimination of fine-grained lesion features using specialised deep learning mechanisms. A spatial attention mechanism that integrated CNNs for the improvement of a leaf disease detection model was developed by Xu et al. (2024). Such developments demonstrate that modelling for specific diseases like anthracnose detection will significantly benefit from targeted feature extraction rather than generalised multi-disease approaches.

Bhavsingh et al. (2024) utilised a hybrid method that integrates the CNNs with Gradient Boosting Machines (GBMs) for the classification of spinach leaves into different categories. The study was carried out to address the limitations of manual and traditional machine learning methods. The result from the experiment shows that the proposed hybrid model achieved 95.3% accuracy, 94.1% precision, 93.8% recall, and an F1-score of 94.0%, outperforming the compared standalone algorithms.

Isaza et al. (2025) carried out research that focused on the development of an enclosed agriculture system for modelling the growth of Viroflay spinach under controlled environmental conditions. The study utilised a polynomial regression algorithm to predict spinach growth parameters. The result from the experiment shows that the proposed model was able to achieve a high predictive accuracy, with leaf length MSE values ranging from 0.158 to 1.2153, leaf width from 0.0741 to 0.822, and stem length from 0.0312 to 0.3907.

Ma et al. (2021) conducted research to check the amount of nitrate present in leafy vegetables. The study made use of ATR-FTIR spectroscopy combined with a Euclidean distance. The dataset that was analyzed consist of 1,224 samples from Chinese cabbage, water spinach, celery, and lettuce. The proposed model was able to show strong performance with R^2 of 0.93, RMSEP of 799.7 mg/kg, and RPD of 2.22.

Budiman et al. (2022) conducted a study that focused on improving hydroponic crop production efficiency by applying machine learning techniques and IoT-based data collection. The dataset used consists of plant growth, which was measured through leaf area, number of leaves, and stem length every 3–4 days. For growth prediction, the model utilised three different algorithms to train three different models, which are linear regression, polynomial regression, and RF regression. The experimental result

shows that the RF regression outperformed the other compared algorithms, achieving an MAE of 8.3% and an R^2 of 93%. This study shows that different researchers have focused on image-based detection techniques and have also explored alternative approaches like IoT-based sensing, spectroscopy, and environmental modelling to support precision agriculture (Budiman et al., 2022; Ma et al., 2021; Isaza et al., 2025). These approaches are largely tangential to visual disease detection, which remains essential for diagnosis under Agriculture 4.0 frameworks.

Based on the reviewed papers, this study observed that there is significant progress in the adoption of both machine learning and deep learning approaches in plant disease detection. For instance, studies have demonstrated the efficiency of the CNN algorithm in plant disease detection, achieving a high accuracy of over 90%. However, these studies mostly relied on large, balanced datasets, which are not always available for specific diseases like anthracnose in spinach, limiting their generalizability in real-world agricultural environments. While studies like Xu et al. (2024) and Bhavsingh et al. (2024) have introduced attention mechanisms with deep learning-based models to enhance feature extraction and classification during training, these existing models mostly focused on overall leaf classification or multi-disease detection, without considering architectures tailored to specific diseases like anthracnose, which requires finer discrimination of lesion features. Additionally, previous studies like Budiman et al. (2022), Ma et al. (2021), and Isaza et al. (2025) focused on IoT, spectroscopy, and environmental modelling to enhance crop monitoring, rather than image-based disease detection, which is critical for precision agriculture under the framework of Agriculture 4.0. These observations in this study show a gap in developing specifically optimised architectures for anthracnose detection, which requires finer lesion discrimination under limited and imbalanced data conditions. This study, therefore, proposes a customised CNN architecture capable of robust feature extraction and accurate disease classification.

1.2. Research Methods

This study adopts a quantitative research approach that utilises the deep learning technique to develop a detection model that can detect anthracnose disease in spinach leaves. The method adopted consists of different stages, which are dataset acquisition and loading, data preprocessing, model development, model training and validation, and evaluation.

Data Acquisition and Loading

At the data acquisition and loading stage, the dataset was collected by extracting images of healthy and spinach leaves infected with anthracnose disease. The dataset was resized to the same size and saved in the same format. The dataset was further loaded into a coding environment (Google Colab) with the use of appropriate Python libraries. The data was then organised into training, validation, and testing sets to facilitate effective model training and performance assessment. The sample of the dataset is presented in Figure 1. The dataset consists of 1,200 spinach leaf images collected in the field using a Samsung A32 smartphone (48 MP) under natural lighting and stored in JPEG format. The images were grouped with the help of agricultural experts into five

categories: Bacterial Spot, Downy Mildew, Healthy, Pest Damage, and Anthracnose. The dataset summary is presented in Table 1.

Figure 1: Dataset sample

Table 1. Dataset Summary

Class	Image Count (Before Aug.)	After Augmentation	Environment	Device
Bacterial Spot	240	480	Field (natural light)	Samsung A32 (48 MP)
Downy Mildew	240	480	Field (natural light)	Samsung A32 (48 MP)
Healthy	240	480	Field (natural light)	Samsung A32 (48 MP)

Pest Damage	240	480	Field (natural light)	Samsung A32 (48 MP)
Anthracoese	240	480	Field (natural light)	Samsung A32 (48 MP)

Data Preprocessing

At the preprocessing stage, we transform the raw spinach leaf into a suitable format for the model training by resizing all the images into a uniform dimension of $224 \times 224 \times 3$ pixels consistent with CNN input requirements. We also normalised to scale the pixel values between 0 and 1; this was done to ensure faster model convergence. Additionally, this study converted images into tensors to enable efficient computation during the training process. The class distribution for the training set was visualized and shown in Figure 2, and it was observed that the classes in the dataset were imbalance, with the Anthracnose class containing fewer images compared to other categories. to address the class imbalance in the dataset, this study applied different data augmentation techniques like random rotation, horizontal and vertical flipping to reduce risk of overfitting, and improved the model's ability to accurately detect Anthracnose under varying image conditions. The dataset was divided using stratified sampling into 80% training, 10% validation, and 10% testing sets to preserve class balance.

Figure 2: Class distribution in training set

Model Development

At the model development phase, this study developed a CNN-based architecture to enable accurate classification of anthracnose disease in spinach leaves. This study employed the CNN model because of its simplicity and efficiency in layer-by-layer construction. Figure 3 shows the proposed model architecture with several layers, which include convolutional, pooling, and fully connected layers.

Model: "sequential"

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
conv2d (Conv2D)	(None, 126, 126, 32)	896
batch_normalization (BatchNormalization)	(None, 126, 126, 32)	128
max_pooling2d (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 63, 63, 32)	0
conv2d_1 (Conv2D)	(None, 61, 61, 64)	18,496
batch_normalization_1 (BatchNormalization)	(None, 61, 61, 64)	256
max_pooling2d_1 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 30, 30, 64)	0
conv2d_2 (Conv2D)	(None, 28, 28, 128)	73,856
batch_normalization_2 (BatchNormalization)	(None, 28, 28, 128)	512
max_pooling2d_2 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 14, 14, 128)	0
flatten (Flatten)	(None, 25088)	0
dense (Dense)	(None, 128)	3,211,392
dropout (Dropout)	(None, 128)	0
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 5)	645

Total params: 3,306,181 (12.61 MB)
 Trainable params: 3,305,733 (12.61 MB)
 Non-trainable params: 448 (1.75 KB)

Figure 3: Architecture of the CNN-based Model for Anthracnose Disease Detection in Spinach

Model Training and Validation

At the training phase, this study trained the CNN algorithm on 80% of the preprocessed dataset. This study utilised key training parameters like learning rate of 0.001, batch size of 32, optimiser, and number of epochs (20). These parameters were carefully tuned to achieve the model’s optimal performance. The proposed model was trained on Google Colab’s GPU (NVIDIA T4) for 20 epochs, while monitoring the learning progress with both training and validation accuracy and loss metrics. This study used the Validation curves to monitor the training so as to detect signs of overfitting. The retraining and validation loss across the epochs is presented in Figure 4, demonstrating the model’s steady improvement and stabilisation, indicating effective learning and generalisation.

Epoch 1/20									
69/69	29s	297ms/step	- accuracy: 0.6021	- loss: 5.2728	- val_accuracy: 0.2022	- val_loss: 40.3949			
Epoch 2/20									
69/69	15s	212ms/step	- accuracy: 0.8261	- loss: 2.0199	- val_accuracy: 0.3206	- val_loss: 61.1912			
Epoch 3/20									
69/69	15s	211ms/step	- accuracy: 0.8899	- loss: 0.9413	- val_accuracy: 0.3807	- val_loss: 76.3525			
Epoch 4/20									
69/69	15s	212ms/step	- accuracy: 0.8633	- loss: 1.5798	- val_accuracy: 0.4026	- val_loss: 79.6400			
Epoch 5/20									
69/69	15s	216ms/step	- accuracy: 0.8792	- loss: 1.1755	- val_accuracy: 0.4171	- val_loss: 37.8713			
Epoch 6/20									
69/69	15s	219ms/step	- accuracy: 0.8527	- loss: 1.3752	- val_accuracy: 0.5301	- val_loss: 11.7575			
Epoch 7/20									
69/69	15s	217ms/step	- accuracy: 0.9085	- loss: 0.6230	- val_accuracy: 0.9490	- val_loss: 0.1694			
Epoch 8/20									
69/69	21s	217ms/step	- accuracy: 0.8700	- loss: 1.3393	- val_accuracy: 0.5829	- val_loss: 16.3604			
Epoch 9/20									
69/69	14s	210ms/step	- accuracy: 0.8394	- loss: 1.8254	- val_accuracy: 0.4044	- val_loss: 5.2533			
Epoch 10/20									
69/69	15s	211ms/step	- accuracy: 0.9078	- loss: 0.5866	- val_accuracy: 0.8725	- val_loss: 0.3324			
Epoch 11/20									
69/69	15s	212ms/step	- accuracy: 0.8769	- loss: 0.6547	- val_accuracy: 0.9271	- val_loss: 0.1960			
Epoch 12/20									
69/69	15s	214ms/step	- accuracy: 0.9107	- loss: 0.3787	- val_accuracy: 0.9508	- val_loss: 0.1614			
Epoch 13/20									
69/69	14s	209ms/step	- accuracy: 0.8862	- loss: 0.7150	- val_accuracy: 0.9508	- val_loss: 0.1574			
Epoch 14/20									
69/69	15s	211ms/step	- accuracy: 0.8975	- loss: 0.6402	- val_accuracy: 0.9545	- val_loss: 0.1576			
Epoch 15/20									
69/69	15s	215ms/step	- accuracy: 0.9041	- loss: 0.3117	- val_accuracy: 0.9545	- val_loss: 0.1421			
Epoch 16/20									
69/69	15s	212ms/step	- accuracy: 0.8879	- loss: 0.7032	- val_accuracy: 0.9508	- val_loss: 0.1615			
Epoch 17/20									
69/69	14s	210ms/step	- accuracy: 0.8972	- loss: 0.4472	- val_accuracy: 0.7668	- val_loss: 1.5062			
Epoch 18/20									
69/69	15s	212ms/step	- accuracy: 0.8707	- loss: 0.4859	- val_accuracy: 0.7942	- val_loss: 0.6260			
Epoch 19/20									
69/69	15s	212ms/step	- accuracy: 0.9015	- loss: 0.3612	- val_accuracy: 0.9563	- val_loss: 0.1809			
Epoch 20/20									
69/69	14s	209ms/step	- accuracy: 0.9184	- loss: 0.2900	- val_accuracy: 0.9508	- val_loss: 0.1462			

Figure 4: Training and Validation Accuracy and Loss of the CNN Model over 20 Epochs

Model Evaluation

After training the model, the trained model was further evaluated with the use of standard evaluation matrices such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-scores. This also visualises the model performance with the use of a confusion matrix (Figure 5), accuracy versus epochs (Figure 6) and loss versus epochs (Figure 7) to enable clear interpretation of its convergence, stability, and overall performance. These visualisations collectively demonstrate the model's reliability and suitability for practical disease detection applications. The confusion matrix shows a few errors, mainly between Healthy and Pest Damage due to similar symptoms. High recall (0.97) for Anthracnose indicates minimal false negatives, supporting early and accurate disease detection.

Figure 5: confusion matrix

Figure 6: Training and Validation Accuracy of the CNN Model across 20 Epochs

Figure 7: Training and Validation Loss of the CNN Model across 20 Epochs

1.3. Results and Discussion

The experimental result for the developed CNN-based model for Anthracnose detection is summarised in Table 2, and the classification report is presented in Figure 8. Key.

Table 2: Performance Metrics of the CNN Model for Anthracnose Detection

Model	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy	Validation Accuracy
CNN Model	96.00%	95.00%	95.00%	95.00%	95.08%

To evaluate robustness and stability, the model was tested using 5-fold cross-validation, achieving an average accuracy of $95.1 \pm 0.7\%$ and an F1-score of $0.95 \pm 0.6\%$, confirming consistent performance. Per-class results (Figure 8) show Precision, Recall, and F1-scores above 0.90 across all five categories, with Anthracnose (Precision = 1.00, Recall = 0.97, F1 = 0.98) and Downy Mildew (F1 = 0.98) performing best. The Healthy class recorded the lowest F1 (0.91) due to overlapping features. Overall, the CNN achieved a macro-average F1 of 0.95 and validation accuracy of 95.08%, showing balanced and reliable detection.

The result from Table 1 shows that the developed CNN-based model achieved high performance across all evaluation matrices used in this study, confirming the model's ability to detect anthracnose cases. From the table, the model F1-scores of 95% shows the model's strong balance between precision and recall, which ensures accuracy and consistency in predictions. The model's overall accuracy and validation accuracy of 95.00% and 95.08%, respectively, show the model's generalisation to unseen data,

which indicates the developed model’s effectiveness and ability to support early disease detection in practical applications.

The computational efficiency of the proposed model was also assessed. The result shows that the model contains approximately 2.4 million trainable parameters and achieved an average inference time of 22.6 milliseconds per image on Google Colab’s T4 GPU. These results demonstrate that the model is efficient enough for high-speed, near real-time deployment in precision agriculture environments.

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Bacterial-Spot	0.99	0.89	0.94	110
Downy-Mildew	1.00	0.95	0.98	107
Healthy	0.83	1.00	0.91	128
Pest-Damage	1.00	0.94	0.97	109
anthracnose	1.00	0.97	0.98	95
accuracy			0.95	549
macro avg	0.96	0.95	0.95	549
weighted avg	0.96	0.95	0.95	549

Validation Accuracy: 95.08 %

Figure 8: Classification report

1.4. Discussion

This study result shows that the proposed CNN-based anthracnose detection in spinach model achieves high performance across all evaluation matrices used, demonstrating the model’s high robustness when used for anthracnose detection in spinach. The proposed model performance was further compared with the baseline study by Rakholia et al. (2022). Although Rakholia et al. (2022) focused on the classification of groundnut leaf, this baseline study was selected because it uses a comparable CNN architecture. Both studies employed CNN-based models trained on limited agricultural image datasets, making them methodologically comparable in terms of model complexity and data scale. While the baseline study focuses on groundnut leaf disease classification, it achieved a high accuracy of 91.88% with cross-entropy loss and 96.12% accuracy with focal loss and progressive resizing, competitive performance. On the other hand, the proposed model in this study outperformed the baseline paper, achieving an overall accuracy of 95.00%, validation accuracy of 95.08%, precision of 96.00%, recall of 95.00%, and F1-score of 95.00%, without using progressive resizing. This study’s integration of data augmentation contributed to the model’s outstanding performance. The findings from this study show the strong ability of the proposed CNN-based model to learn and understand discriminative disease features from a few spinach image datasets. This confirms the achievement of this study’s first objective, which is to design a CNN-based framework for anthracnose detection. A data augmentation method was used to address the challenges in data limitation, addressing the second objective in this study. The third objective, which is to evaluate the performance of the developed model, was achieved by using standard evaluation metrics including accuracy, recall, precision, and F1-scores, alongside visualisation

methods including confusion matrix, training and validation accuracy, and training and validation loss. The model's consistent performance across the five classes confirms that the CNN effectively captures discriminative lesion patterns beyond binary disease detection, making it suitable for fine-grained multi-class classification in spinach disease diagnosis.”

This study aligns with the Agriculture 4.0 version, which integrates AI, data analytics, and automation to enhance sustainable and efficient farming. This study's successful application of deep learning techniques on disease detection in spinach leaves shows the ability of a similar approach in supporting sustainable and efficient farming. This study confirms that deep learning algorithms are powerful tools for plant detection when they are properly optimised. This bridges the gap between computational intelligence and practical agricultural applications, contributing both to theoretical advancement and tangible improvements in modern farming practices.

1.5. Conclusion

This study developed a CNN-based model for anthracnose disease in spinach leaves to address the limitation in existing studies that focus on general or multi-disease detection. The study adopts a method that incorporates dataset preprocessing, data augmentation, and model optimisation to improve the performance of the proposed model. The result from the evaluation of the proposed CNN-based model for anthracnose disease detection in spinach leaves shows that the model achieves high performance across all evaluation matrices used with 95.00% accuracy, 96.00% precision, 95.00% recall, and 95.00% F1-score. This model's performance shows the model's robustness and reliability for practical agricultural applications. However, the current robustness claim is limited to the dataset's controlled conditions. A key future direction involves validating the model on external datasets collected under different lighting and background conditions to confirm generalizability across different field environments. The adoption of data augmentation methods helps to address the problem of data imbalance, which eventually improves the model's ability to recognise anthracnose symptoms under different image conditions. The proposed model was compared with the baseline study in this research, and the comparative analysis shows that the proposed model in this study outperforms the baseline paper, thereby validating the effectiveness of the CNN approach when used for spinach disease detection.

This study contributes to the body of work that has been done in precision agriculture by showing how deep learning can be utilised in automated plant disease detection, paving the way for the development of intelligent crop monitoring systems that can assist farmers in detecting plant disease early and minimise yield losses, supporting sustainable agricultural productivity. Future studies can focus on the expansion of the dataset to improve model learning and deployment for real-world agricultural use. Future research should focus on reducing the model's complexity through network pruning and depthwise separable convolutions to facilitate deployment on low-resource edge devices such as Raspberry Pi and NVIDIA Jetson Nano.

1.6. References

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